

Proportional Odds Modelling of Hiv Infection Among Pregnant Women in Imo State

Nwagwu, Glory C¹, Obasi, Chinedu K², and Nduka, Modestus U³

^{1,2}Department of Statistics, Kingsley Ozumba Mbadiwe University, Ideato, Imo State, Nigeria.

²Department of Mathematics, Kingsley Ozumba Mbadiwe University, Ideato, Imo State, Nigeria.

Abstract- The HIV virus is a cankerworm that is bedeviling human-kind, with sequel advancement to Acquired Immuno-deficiency Syndrome (AIDS), if not properly managed can have effect on the socio-demographic factors. The study aimed at determining the impact of socio-demographic factors that affects HIV status of pregnant women in Imo state using a Proportional Odds Model. It was discovered that single women within the Age (15-19) years and resident in the rural area were the factors that contributed to the reason why these pregnant women are prone to contacting HIV/AIDS infection in Imo State.

Keywords – HIV, AIDS, Proportional odds modelling, Socio-demographic factors, Pregnant women etc.

I. INTRODUCTION

The HIV virus otherwise called the Human Immuno-deficiency Virus (HIV) has been a cankerworm that is bedeviling human-kind. It is a retrovirus known to cause human Immune-deficiency infection, with sequel advancement to Acquired Immuno-deficiency Syndrome (AIDS) if not properly managed. AIDS is a distinct syndrome associated with severe and life-threatening clinical conditions. It remains one of the world's most significant public health challenges. Human Immuno-deficiency Virus (HIV) attacks the body's immune system, gradually destroying its ability to fight infections and certain cancers. HIV can develop into Acquired Immuno-Deficiency syndrome (AIDs), if left untreated. HIV is of concern because it has serious impact on virtually every facet of human endeavor to include socio-economic activities with special emphasis on how it affects the fertility of the infected individual (Salu, et al. 2018).

HIV testing is the best way for treatment care and support services. Checking of HIV status will definitely empower individuals and couples in taking measures to prevent HIV acquisition or onward transmission. For those already infected, a positive result is necessary to access treatment and, in the case of pregnant mothers it helps them for the Prevention of Mother to Child Transmission (PMTCT) services (Ali, 2015). In the case of communities, awareness of HIV status through testing could reduce HIV related stigma and discrimination. Population related surveys provide national level prevalence estimates and the opportunity for behavioral, social and other biological information (Stover, 2004).

The progressive increase of cases of HIV/AIDS in women in reproductive age contributed for an increase in the rates of

vertical transmission, which has been shown to be an important challenge for public health policies (Sama, et al 2017).

According to Stover (2004), fertility is one of the components of population change in any country therefore; any disease affecting it will have serious impact on demographic transition. He further states that Nigeria has experienced high fertility levels over the last two decades despite numerous policies oriented programs by the government and international agencies. He further advised that negative influence and poor planning on fertility has a psychological sense in reducing fertility.

According to Alvarez (2011) he emphasized that Logistic Regression Model is a bid to determine the influence of Socio-Demographic factors on HIV in pregnant women. His study reveals that categorical responses on pregnancy outcome in terms of some predictors will determine the goodness of fit, as well as the validity of assumption. In many epidemiological studies on socio-demographic influence on HIV infected pregnant women, the model (Ordinal Logistic Regression) can be utilized as a tool to model data. Ordinal Logistic Regression is a Statistical Model used to model the relationship between variables with Ordinal-Scale response variables with continuous/categorical explanatory variables.

OBJECTIVE

To fit an appropriate Ordinal Logistic Regression Model to the Socio-demographic risk factors of HIV/AIDS infection among pregnant women.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

Data for this study were collected from the medical record unit as well as the HIV unit of the Federal Medical Centre, Owerri. The data comprises of the socio-demographic factors and HIV

status of pregnant women from 2023 to 2024. The variables under study include “Age”, “Residence”, “Senatorial Zone”, “Marital Status”, “Contraceptive use”, “Educational level”, “Religion”, “Employment status” and “HIV status” of the pregnant women.

CATEGORIZATION OF VARIABLES OF THE STUDY

Table 1: Categories of the dependent variable with the corresponding codes

Categories of HIV	Grading of HIV infection by CD count	Code
HIV negative	500 – 1700 cells/μl	0
HIV Positive	200 – 499 cells/μl	1
Full blown AIDS	< 200 cells /μl	2

SOURCE: Federal Medical Center (FMC), Owerri (2024)

Table 2: List of independent variables with respective names, categories and codes

Socio-Demographic factors	Categories	Codes	Variable Notation
Age group	15-19	0	X ₁
	20-24	1	
	25-29	2	
	30-34	3	
	35 and above	4	
Residence	Urban	0	X ₂
	Rural	1	
Senatorial zone	Owerri	0	X ₃
	Okigwe	1	
	Orlu	2	
Marital status	Single	0	X ₄
	Married	1	
	Divorced	2	
Contraceptive use	Ever users	0	X ₅
	Never users	1	
Educational level	Primary	0	X ₆
	Secondary	1	
	Tertiary	2	
Religion	Christianity	0	X ₇
	Islam	1	
	Traditional	2	
Employment status	Working	0	X ₈
	Not working	1	

SOURCE: NWAGWU (2024)

METHOD OF ANALYSIS

Since the dependent variable (i.e., HIV status) is categorical with more than two levels with natural ordering viz., “negative”, “positive” and “full blown AIDS” respectively, then the appropriate method of data analysis is Ordinal Logistic Regression (Proportional Odds Model) or for describing the nature of the data. In addition, descriptive statistical analyses were used.

Descriptive statistical analysis

Descriptive statistics used in this study are tables, bar charts and percentages. They are used to describe the frequency distribution and percentage of HIV status of pregnant women according to their socio-demographic characteristics.

General Ordinal Logistic Regression Model (Proportional Odds Model)

Ordinal logistic regression is a type of logistic regression that focuses on predicting the value of a categorical dependent variable with more than two ordinal categories based on a set of independent variables which may be continuous and/or categorical.

The linear statistical model for implementing ordinal logistic regression is given in Hosmer and Lemeshow (2000) as:

$$link(\theta_j) = \alpha_j + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_k X_k + e_j$$

, $j = 1, 2, \dots, k - 1$ (3.2)

where,

$link(\theta_j)$ is the link function

θ_j is the cumulative probability of the jth category

for the ith case

$link(\theta_j)$ is the log-likelihood that a patient falls into

one of the k levels of the dependent variable

α_j is the threshold parameter for the jth category

$X_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, k)$ are the values of the predictors

for the ith case

$\beta_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, k)$ is the regression coefficient

associated with the ith predictor variable

k is the number of regression coefficients

Assumptions of Ordinal Logistic Regression Model

In order to estimate the parameters of the Ordinal Logistic Regression Model stated in (3.2), the following assumptions are made:

- (i.) The dependent variable should be measured at ordinal level
- (ii.) Ordinal independent variables must be either continuous or categorical
- (iii.) There should be no multicollinearity among the explanatory variables

(iv.) The observations are independently drawn

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

III. RESULTS / DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Table 3: Frequency (Percentage) distribution of HIV status of pregnant women in Imo State by their socio-demographic characteristics

SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS	HIV STATUS OF PREGNANT WOMEN IN IMO STATE			
	NEGATIVE	POSITIVE	AIDS	TOTAL
AGE				
15-19	(60.3)10	(28.6)4	(11.1)2	(100.0)14
20-24	(78.6)11	(21.4)3	(0.0)0	(100.0)14
25-29	(81.2)26	(18.8)6	(0.0)0	(100.0)32
30-34	(80.6)25	(12.9)4	(6.5)2	(100.0)31
35 and above	(87.8)7	(11.1)1	(1.1)1	(100.0)9
RESIDENCE				
URBAN	(84.3)59	(14.3)10	(1.4)1	100.0)70
RURAL	(66.7)20	(26.7)8	(6.7)2	(100.0)30
MARITAL STATUS				
SINGLE	(46.6)12	(12.8)6	(40.6)2	(100.0)50
MARRIED	(62.8)6	(26.6)70	(10.6)0	(100.0)22
DIVORCED	(60.0)31	(10.0)6	(30.0)1	(100.0)38

SOURCE: Nwagwu (2024)

The values in brackets () are values showing the percentages of the HIV status of the pregnant women. The values that are not in bracket are values showing the frequencies of the HIV of the pregnant women.

Charts representation of HIV status of pregnant women in Imo state by their socio-demographic characteristics

Figure 4.1: HIV status of pregnant women by age

Figure 4.2: HIV status of pregnant women by residence

Figure 4.3: HIV status of pregnant women by marital status

IV. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Result from Table 4.3 went further to show that pregnant women within the ages of 15-19 are infected with HIV/AIDS. This result is in support of the argument made in (Amoko, et al 2016) which states that there is a statistical significant association between ages of people above 17 years.

Result from Table 3 shows that pregnant women within the ages of 15-19 years are more infected with HIV/AIDS. Also from the result in Figure 4.1, 4.2, 4.3 it can be inferred that HIV/AIDS is predominant among pregnant single women within the ages of 15-19years who are resident in the rural area of the State

V. CONCLUSION

This work discussed the application of ordinal logistic regression model (also called the proportional odds model) in

modeling the effect of socio-demographic variables on the HIV status of pregnant women in Imo state. The model was adopted in the analysis of data due to the fact that HIV status is categorical variables with natural ordering viz: Negative, Positive and Full Blown AIDS. In order to conduct a quantitative analysis on data collected on such categorical variables, we coded Negative as “0”, Positive as “1” and full blown AIDS as “2”. Results obtained from the analysis showed that some socio-demographic variables are statistically significant to the model. It was discovered that Age (15-19) years, Resident (rural), and Marital Status (single), were all factors that contributed to the reason why these pregnant women are prone to contacting HIV/AIDS infection in Imo State. It is recommended for future researchers that Religious institutions should assist the teeming youth from 15-19 years of age by preaching religious values and sound moral instructions which will help guide them against contacting the deadly disease.

REFERENCES

1. Abreu, M. N. S., Arminda, L. S., Clareci, S. C., and Waleska, T. C. (2008). Ordinal logistic regression models. Application in quality of life studies *Cad. Saúde Pública*, Rio de Janeiro, 24 Sup 4:S581-S591.
2. Agresti, A. (1990). *Categorical data Analysis*. John Wiley and sons, Newyork.
3. Ali, M. A. (2015). Logistic Regression to determine the Relationship between HIV Testing, HIV Knowledge and Attitude among women in Kenya. University of Nairobi, Institution of Tropical and Infectious Diseases.
4. Alvarez, G. (2011). Trends and risk factors for HIV infection among young pregnant women in rural India. *International Journal of Infectious Diseases*.
5. Amoko A., Ayinmode, B. A., Odeigah, L.O., Alabi, K.M., Ajiboye, P.O., and Adunmo, E. O. (2016). Prevalence of depression and socio-demographic characteristics of HIV infected patients seen by family physicians at university of Ilorin Teaching Hospital, Ilorin Nigerian. *Nigerian Journal of family Practice*. Vol. 7 Pg 1.
6. Gujarati, D.N. (2003). *Basic Econometrics*, Mcgraw Hill higher Education United States Military Academy West point Newyork. Fourth edition.
7. Hosmer, D.W., and Lemeshow, S. (2000). *Applied logistic regression*. 2nd Edition, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York.doi:10.1002/0471722146
8. Salu, O. B., Nwaokorie, F. O, Banwo, T. E., Oke, B. O., James, A. B. and Omilabu, S. A. (2018). Detection Of Human Immunodeficiency Virus Among Individuals Presenting with Febrile Illness In Lagos, Nigeria. Department of Medical Microbiology and Parasitology, College of Medicine, University of Lagos, Lagos State, Nigeria; Virology Unit Laboratory, Central Research Laboratory, College of Medicine, University of Lagos, Lagos Nigeria. *African Journal Of Clinical And Experimental Microbiology* Isbn1595-689x Vol19 No.3.
9. Sama, C. B., Feteh, V. F., Tindong, M., Tanyi, J. T., Bihle, N. M., and Angwafo, F. F. (2017). Prevalence of maternal HIV infection and knowledge on mother -to -child transmission of HIV and its prevention among antenatal care attendees in a rural area in Northwest Cameroon. *PLoS One*. 2017;12(2):e0172102. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0172102.eCollection.
a. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0172102>
10. Stover, J. (2004). The influence of HIV/AIDS on fertility, Department of Epidemiology, University of Ghana. Reports on global AIDS epidemic, 4ed, Joint United Nations programme on HIV/AIDS
11. World Health Organisation. (2023). Normalizing Awareness for HIV status